

Hazards and Hydropower:

A Tale of an Industrial Collections Move at Ingenium

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Ingenium sits on the traditional and unceded territory of the Algonquin-Anishinaabeg peoples.

We recognize that our work in cultural heritage has had, and continues to have, significant impact on Indigenous peoples across this land.

As we are speaking about industrial and hydroelectric heritage, we acknowledge the devastating impact that environmental pollutants, and hydroelectric power generation have had on Indigenous peoples and the ecosystems they have protected for thousands of years. We also acknowledge the colonial nature of the heritage field, as well as the industrial colonization of Turtle Island.

A photograph of a modern building facade. The building features a mix of materials: light-colored vertical metal panels, large glass windows, and a section with diagonal metal slats. A row of small, rectangular windows is visible on the right side. The sky is a clear, light blue.

The Setting & Characters

Ingenium: 3 national museums

New purpose-built storage facility

The 2421 Reserve Collection

Project Background

- 5500 industrial artifacts
- Most from the Ontario Hydro “Museum of Electrical Progress”
- Also contained Ingenium’s radioactive stores

The 2421 Reserve Collection

Project Background

Issues in the old collections storage:

- Overcrowded
- Limited access
- As a result, hazard mitigation was not possible

The Characters

Project Background

- 3 Conservators
- 1 Cataloguer
- Artifact Handlers
- Mount-Maker
- Curators
- Contractors - for the heaviest stuff
- Contractors - PCBs, asbestos (Type 3), refrigerants

Collections Risk Management at Ingenium

Collection Hazard Management at Ingenium

Project Background

Legal obligations

and

Professional obligations for conservators:

- Section 43 of the *CAC and CAPC Code of Ethics and Guidance for Practice* (2000)

A New Collections Risk Management Plan

Project Background

New Collections Risk Management (CRM) plan in 2018

- Prioritises human safety
 - Goal: “Access for All”
- Standardises labelling
- Artifact Hazard *Risk Assessments and Safe Work Practices* (RASPs) for each hazard type

Hazardous cadmium corrosion in our collection.

32 RASPs... and counting

Project Background

- Animal Biohazard
- Antimony Hazard
- Asbestos Hazard
- Battery Hazard
- Beryllium Hazard
- Cadmium Hazard
- Calcium Carbide Hazard
- Cathode Ray Tube & Vacuum Tube Hazard
- Chemical Product Hazard
- Compressed Gas Hazard
- Dust and Fibre Hazard
- Explosives and Ammunition Hazard
- Fire Extinguisher Hazard
- Flour Hazard
- Fuel Hazard
- Human Biohazard
- Large Sized Artifact Hazard
- Lead Hazard
- Medication and Drug Hazard
- Mercury Hazard
- Mould and Fungus Hazard
- Oil and Grease Hazard
- PCB Hazard
- Pesticide Hazard
- Plastics Hazards
- Poor Condition Tire Hazard
- Radiation Hazard
- Refrigerants Hazard
- Sharps Hazard
- Split Rim Tire Hazard
- Stored Electrical Energy Hazard
- Stored Mechanical Energy Hazard

Artifact Hazard Risk Assessments and Safe Work Practices (RASPs)

Project Background

Lead Artifact Risk Assessment

Ingenium Canada Collection Risk Management - RASP

Consult Risk Management Policy for CSTMC.

Consult Enterprise Lead Hazard Resources <http://openstext.org/cstmc/links/9560511> or your Manager for more information.

What is it?

Lead is a grey-black heavy metal (chemical symbol **Pb**). It can be mixed with other metals to form alloys, such as pewter. Lead oxides are corrosion products of lead and lead alloys.

Why is it hazardous?

Lead causes long-term damage to organs, can cause cancer and can cause harm to fertility and fetal development. Other lead-caused illnesses include gastrointestinal ailments, anemia, and kidney disease.

Inhalation and ingestion of lead oxide particles must be avoided.

Where is it?

Lead metal and alloys can be found in all parts of the collection. Lead-formed alloys can be found in ammunition, pipes, cable coverings/wrappings, building material, solder, radiation shielding, gaskets, seals, sealing pastes, bearings, collapsible tubes, and fishing weights.

White lead was mixed with linseed oil to prepare canvas roofs such as railway passenger cars and cabooses.

Lead is also used in ceramic glazes and as a stabilizer in plastics.

Lead was used extensively as a corrosion inhibitor and pigment in paints is now banned for use in public and residential buildings. Lead is present in the electrodes of Lead-Acid batteries.

Leaded gasoline was present in Canada until 1990. Lead residues may be present in exhaust...

What does it look like?

Lead is a blue-grey metal with a dull surface texture. Lead oxides can be white and powdery appearance. Lead oxides can also be yellow and red.

Lead pigments include, but are not limited to:

- White Lead (lead II carbonate),
- red Litharge (lead monoxide),
- yellow lead chromate (PbCrO4)
- Naples yellow (Lead II Antimonate),
- red Minium (lead tetroxide),
- yellow lead chromate
- red-orange lead molybdate.

Lead paints are not visibly different to non-leaded paints. It may be qualitatively detected using Plumbosm strips. Suspected lead containing materials should be analysed by an external expert for confirmation.

Ingenium Canada Collection Risk Management - RASP

Lead Artifact Hazard Safe Work Practice

Collections Steps IF HAZARD FOUND OR SUSPECTED		Conservation Steps IF HAZARD FOUND OR SUSPECTED	
PPE minimum:	Nitrile gloves, P100 respirator, goggles, lab-coat	PPE minimum:	Nitrile gloves, P100 respirator, goggles, lab-coat
Notification:	For loose lead oxidation dusts or suspected flaking lead paint, contact Conservation Manager.	Notification:	None
Label:	<p>Lead (& oxidation products) / Plomb (et produits d'oxydation)</p> <p>Danger</p> <p>Cat. #: No. de Cat.</p> <p>See EMu & SDS for more information Consultez EMu & FDS pour plus d'information</p>		Label:
Emu info:	Hazard Field: "Yes" "Lead [state and where]" Add Lead SDS to Multimedia Tab	Emu info:	Hazard Field: "Yes" "Lead [state type and where]" Add Lead SDS to Catalogue Multimedia Tab. Add printed SDS to Condition Record if preparing.
Action:	If loose lead oxidation particulates, seal in polyethylene zipper bags or plastic sheet so as to prevent transfer. Consult Conservation to assess presence of lead.	Action:	Remove loose corrosion products. Use ULPA vacuum. Test flaking paint for lead. Consolidate flaking paint if needed.
Storage & Handling:	Store lead artifacts and lead oxidation products in a secure location. Do not use regular waste and materials and label. Dispose in for disposal. Wash hands with soap and water. Launder clothing/rags with Lead detergent.	Storage & Handling:	Consolidate, seal, or wrap unconsolidated flaking lead paint.
Cleanup & Disposal:	Dispose of treatment waste in container as per procedure. Wet-wipe work surface. Wash hands with soap and water. Launder contaminated clothing/rags with Lead detergent.	Cleanup & Disposal:	Dispose of treatment waste in container as per procedure. Wet-wipe work surface. Wash hands with soap and water. Launder contaminated clothing/rags with Lead detergent.

Note that RASPs are internal documents that are continuously updated as our work practices change. They should not be seen as official recommendations from the Government of Canada.

Labelling

Project Background

Artifact labelling:

1. Printed labels attached to artifacts
2. Flag in KE EMu museum database

Based on the Standard Global Harmonized System (GHS)

Mercury / Mercure

Danger

Fatal if inhaled.
May damage fertility or the unborn child.
Causes damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure.
Very toxic to aquatic life.
Very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects.
Obtain special instructions before use.
Do not handle until all safety precautions have been read and understood.
Do not breathe dust/fume/gas/mist/vapours/spray.
Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
Do not eat, drink, or smoke when using this product.
Use only outdoors or in a well-ventilated area.
Avoid release to the environment.
Wear protective gloves/protective clothing/eye protection/face protection.
In case of inadequate ventilation wear respiratory protection.
IF INHALED: Remove person to fresh air and keep comfortable for breathing. Immediately call a POISON CENTER/doctor/
IF exposed or concerned: Get medical advice/attention.
Get medical advice/attention if you feel unwell.
Collect spillage.
Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep container tightly closed.
Store locked up.
Dispose of contents/container to an approved waste disposal site.

Mortel par inhalation.
Peut nuire à la fertilité ou au fœtus.
Risque avéré d'effets graves pour les organes à la suite d'expositions répétées ou d'une exposition prolongée.
Très toxique pour les organismes aquatiques.
Très toxique pour les organismes aquatiques, entraîne des effets néfastes à long terme.
Se procurer les instructions avant utilisation.
Ne pas manipuler avant d'avoir lu et compris toutes les précautions de sécurité.
Ne pas respirer les poussières/fumées/gaz/brouillards/vapeurs/aérosols.
Se laver les mains soigneusement après manipulation.
Ne pas manger, boire ou fumer en manipulant ce produit.
Utiliser seulement en plein air ou dans un endroit bien ventilé.
Éviter le rejet dans l'environnement.
Porter des gants de protection/des vêtements de protection/un équipement de protection des yeux/du visage.
Lorsque la ventilation du local est insuffisante porter un équipement de protection respiratoire.
EN CAS D'INHALATION : Transporter la personne à l'extérieur et la maintenir dans une position où elle peut confortablement respirer. Appeler immédiatement un CENTRE ANTIPOISON /un médecin/
EN CAS d'exposition prouvée ou suspectée : Demander un avis médical/Consulter un médecin.
Demander un avis médical/Consulter un médecin en cas de malaise.
Recueillir le produit répandu.
Stocker dans un endroit bien ventilé. Maintenir le récipient fermé de manière étanche.
Garder sous clé.
Éliminer le contenu/récipient dans une installation d'élimination des déchets agréée

Cat. #:
No. de Cat:

See EMu & SDS for more information
Consultez EMu & FDS pour plus d'informations

! WARNING

SPLIT RIM TIRES
Do Not Inflate
Consult tire expert

Front PSI: Rear PSI:

! AVERTISSEMENT

ROUES À JAUNTE FENDUE
Ne Gonflez Pas
Consultez un expert de pneus

avant lb/po²: arrière lb/po²:

Cat #: / No. de Cat:

Flagging in museum database

Project Background

19541
[1969.1317.001] - Artifact - FITCHBURG - (Engine, steam)
0
[1969.1317.001] - Artefact - FITCHBURG - (Machine à vapeur)

Assessment Status
By: Wagner Riddle, Jacqueline - CSTMC

Report / Status
Condition Report: No::Non

Inspection, Action, and Hazards

Oil, Coolant, etc.:

Required Action:

Action Taken: Patched & encapsulated friable asbestos. See Conservation report.
Vacuumed overall.

Hazards: Yes
.001 Asbestos insulation around central housing, exposed areas were extremely friable. Patched & encapsulated. See Conservation report.
.001 PCB wipe test taken from lubricator box, Result: 10.3 ug/100cm2. See Conservation report (Updated 12/Nov/2021, J. Riddle).
.002 and .003 not yet assessed

Object Art. Object Art. Context Art. References Art. Details Art. Lexicon Art. Composition Assess Start Infest. Assess Stability Assess As

riddjacq Conservator emucstmc

Case Study 1:
**A tale of asbestos in two
steam engines**

Corliss steam engine (1980.0526)

Asbestos Hazard

The Corliss steam engine (1980.0526) in the 2421 Reserve collections storage.

Corliss steam engine (1980.0526)

Asbestos Hazard

The Corliss steam engine had over 3 metres squared of friable asbestos in the engine housing.

- Ingenium conservators have Type 1 & 2 Ontario Asbestos Certifications
 - Up to **1 m²** of friable asbestos
- Over **1 m²** is classified as “Type 3” and must be performed by specialised asbestos contractors
 - Requires building an enclosure
- Over **3 m²** of friable asbestos present

Corliss steam engine (1980.0526)

Asbestos Hazard

Type 3 enclosure being built.

Type 3 enclosure during asbestos abatement.

Corliss steam engine (1980.0526)

Asbestos Hazard

After treatment, showing the canvas patches with white encapsulant material.

Uniflow steam engine (1969.1317)

Asbestos Hazard

The Fitchburg steam engine (1969.1317) in the 2421 Reserve collections storage.

Uniflow steam engine (1969.1317)

Asbestos Hazard

- Asbestos insulation on most surfaces of steam housing
- Seams and damaged areas revealing friable asbestos

A seam and damaged areas showing friable asbestos insulation.

Uniflow steam engine (1969.1317)

Asbestos Hazard

- Wore personal protective equipment
- HEPA vacuumed before & after work
- Soaked area with a dilute consolidant (Childers CP-240)
- Encapsulated with canvas patch and thicker consolidant (Childers CP-211)
- Disposal of PPE and treatment materials as hazardous waste

Consolidating the friable asbestos.

Uniflow steam engine (1969.1317)

Asbestos Hazard

- 1.5 hours total (incl. report, photos, treatment, clean-up)
- Successfully mitigated the hazard
- In-painting possible in the future

After consolidation/ encapsulation of friable asbestos with CP-211 and CP-240 and application of canvas patches.

Asbestos consolidants used at Ingenium

Asbestos Hazard

- Childers CHIL-LOCK CP-240
 - Used for temporarily sealing asbestos fibres before encapsulation
 - Dries clear, colourless
 - Water based emulsion (10% solids), proprietary
 - SDS: contains chlorinated paraffins
- Childers CHIL-LOCK CP-211
 - Used to encapsulate asbestos
 - Dries white, opaque
 - Water based polymeric emulsion (74% solids), proprietary
 - SDS: contains cellulose, calcium carbonate, titanium dioxide, crystalline silica

Consolidating asbestos on a vacuum tube.

A tale of two steam engines

Asbestos Hazard

Contracted specialist heavy machinery movers, moving the steam engine (1969.1317).

Case Study 2:

A tale of a radioactive balance

A tale of a radioactive balance

Radiation Hazard

- Manufactured by Oertling and used until 1935
- Used to weigh the first radium mined in Canada

A balance and associated tools (1969.1002) used to weigh the first radium mined in Canada.

A tale of a radioactive balance

Radiation Hazard

- Gamma radiation measured with RadEye G-10 meter
 - Readings between 2 and 12 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$
 - 83 hours to Annual Public Dose Limit
- Radioactive dust is a concern

Measuring radiation on a scale used to weigh the first radium mined in Canada.

A balance on the move

Radiation Hazard

- Simple solution!
- Wore PPE to protect from exposure to radioactive dust
- Draped in plastic to contain during move
- Plastic covering removed after move and disposed of as radioactive waste

The balance ready to move.

Measuring radiation doses

Radiation Hazard

- Meters
 - RadEye G-10 measures gamma (γ) radiation
 - Dosimeter 3007A, measures alpha (α) and beta (β) radiation
- Personal dosimeters
 - Whole body and ring dosimeters

Examples of radiation meters and personal dosimeters.

Preparing the new radioactive storage room

Radiation Hazard

- Consultation with the Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission to ensure compliance of all processes

New radioactive storage room

Radiation Hazard

- Radon gas sensor
 - Visual alarm (light)
 - Ventilation to outdoors
 - Notification to building operator
- Less than 2.5 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ in hallway, adjacent rooms
- Reviewed by Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission (CNSC)

The balance in the new radioactive storage room

Case Study 3:

A tale of PCBs in a tape recorder-player

Tape recorder-player

PCBs Hazard, >50 ppm

Tape recorder-player (1996.0284)

Artifact background

- Used 1963-1996 in Nanaimo, British Columbia
- Used in underground emergency headquarters bunker
- For use in case of nuclear attack

Tape recorder-player

PCBs Hazard, >50 ppm

- 6 capacitors, melting potting material
- End caps marked “Pyranol”
- Wipe test result: **32100**
µg/100 cm²
- Over legal limit of 50 ppm

Tape recorder-player (1996.0284)

What on Earth is a PCB?

PCBs Hazard

- Polychlorinated biphenyl compounds
- Highly-regulated
- Consistency varies from thin oil to waxy solid
- Wide variety of environmental and health concerns
- Commonly found in electrical, hydraulic, printing equipment

Chemical structure of PCBs, and examples of artifacts containing PCBs.

PCBs Legislation

PCBs Hazard

- PCBs are highly regulated:
 - Canada: Environmental Protection Act (1999), *PCB Regulations (SOR/2008-273)*
 - Worldwide: United Nations Environment Programme (1999)
- Laws govern labelling, reporting, and disposal
- **Museums are not legally permitted to store artifacts containing material with >50 ppm of PCBs**

uncatalogued PCB capacitors and transformers

PCBs Case Study: Tape recorder-player (1996.0284)

Artifact containing capacitors >50 ppm

- 6 capacitors, melting potting material
- End caps marked “Pyranol”
- Wipe test result: **32100 $\mu\text{g}/100 \text{ cm}^2$**
- Over legal limit of 50 ppm

1 of 6 PCB capacitors inside the artifact, with melting potting material. The cap melted off the capacitor.

PCBs Case Study: Tape recorder-player (1996.0284)

Artifact containing capacitors >50 ppm

- Capacitors removed, documented and disposed of
- Work completed with a specialised PCB mitigation contractor

BEFORE

AFTER

Removal of black cylindrical PCB capacitor.

A Tale of Mercury:
**Packing a collection of
hydroelectric meters**

Packing a collection of electric meters

Mercury Hazard

- More than 30 crates of uncatalogued electric meters, needed hazard assessment before move
- ~100 meters per crate

Crates of mixed electric meters

Hidden mercury : switches

Mercury Hazard

meter containing mercury switch with cellulose nitrate cover

meter containing mercury switch

Mercury type meters

Mercury Hazard

- Sangamo type D meters, direct current
- Ferranti type FH meters, continuous current meters

Loose mercury

FILLED WITH
MERCURY!

Packing a collection of electricity meters

Mercury Hazard

Mercury spill kit from Mercury Instruments USA

Hazard diagnostics: Mercury vapour sensor

Mercury Hazard

- VM-3000 mercury vapour monitor purchased for new mercury collections storage area

New mercury storage area

New mercury vapour monitor

Conclusions

The Numbers: Hazards in the 2421 Reserve Collection

Conclusions

Over **5500** artifacts moved to their new home

1133 hazards identified, including:

- **439** artifacts containing asbestos/ACM
 - **436** asbestos artifacts remediated by conservation
 - **3** asbestos artifacts remediated by contractors
- **345** radioactive artifacts packed for radioactive storage
- **33** artifacts containing mercury separated to chem storage
- **32** artifacts PCBs identified

radioactive gyroscope reads “do not jar. handle like eggs”

A new building!

- Move completed on time
- Safer, more accessible storage

A successful collaborative effort!

Thank you. Any questions?

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Special thanks to Alyson Tang for her contributions to the 2421 Reserve Collection move from 2020-2021, our manager Erin Secord for her support and to the collections move staff at Ingenium for being generally awesome.

or on Twitter [@SciTechPreserv](https://twitter.com/SciTechPreserv)

Canada

IngeniumCanada.org